
Online E-Campus Recruitment Process of Muthoot Finance Ltd.

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Abstract :

Online Campus Recruitment is the most widely performed and most sought to be preferred mode of graduate selection from the campus today. With super-modern automated systems and super process excellence methodologies applied in the business with renewed focus on quality, even manpower hiring has also been structured as an online flow system for steady results. Muthoot Finance LTD. has been Srinivas Institute of Management Studies' esteemed recruiter for MBA Campus adopting an automated approach flow in their campus recruitment process. Therefore, through this research paper, we have attempted to understand company's e-procedure and know the fact to determine the process meaning to our students, stakeholders, the online or e-recruitment domain and entire industry.

Keywords or Index Terms : Online Campus Recruitment, E-Campus Hiring, E-Recruitment Process Analysis, Online Manpower Selection, E-Hiring Analysis

I. Introduction :

The current age involves e-recruitment through intense application of technologies and social media in entire hiring process plus HR back end or operations which also otherwise known as e-HRM. E-Recruiting industry today has reached up to a situation where major recruiters are experimenting various different ways of doing e-recruiting by conducting e-interviews as well as techniques to bring in smoothness on to their digital hiring procedures. Companies have realized that e-recruitment will save them considerable cost and time resources. The competition is in e-recruitment industry today is how one company's e-recruitment process is different from other companies and whose procedures yields better results. Muthoot Finance Ltd, a leading NBFC of India and recruiter from Srinivas Institute of Management Studies' SIMS adopted online

recruitment approach for 2018 MBA Hiring. Therefore, through this study, an attempt is made to document the case of Muthoot Finance Ltd to know how this company conducts its online recruitment.

II. Objectives of the Study :

To inform the stakeholders of this research on the progress presently taking place in e-recruitment domain. To determine the credibility of company's e-recruiting procedure thereby in turn understand its viability or fungibility from futuristic perspectives. To advance suggestions to the company based on process analysis on any adding any new features or eliminate resource wastages taking place currently.

III. Research Methodology :

Data is collected through direct interaction with (a) Company HR (b) experimented process as a real implementation of the company's actual program in campus for student focus group, and final student focus group interview who underwent e-campus recruitment selection. Gathered Data from focus group is analysed and interpreted through ABCD Model (Aithal et al. 2015) for making findings. Analysis and Interpreted information are further displayed through tabular representation for making inferences and conclusions.

IV. System or Process Identified in Muthoot Finance Ltd's online recruitment process at SIMS :

Participating student registers his profile online with a link provided by company HR Team for screening and CV plagiarism checking. The qualified students are motivated to refer company profile, role and management information online. Post this step, the qualified students attend a pre-placement presentation by company HR in campus and undergo a Group Discussion GD. Qualified Students in the Group Discussion will undergo an online employability test at campus hosted for the company by their assessment partner HirePro. Selected Candidates in the test process then attended a final interview with business team who made final decision on candidate selection.

V. ABCD Analysis Listing to the Muthoot Finance Ltd e-recruitment process :

The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of Muthoot Finance e-recruiting framework are listed below :

1. Advantages :

1.1 Advantages to Company

- E-interviews are trouble free as date/day arrangement of the interviews can be easily executed from the company offices.
- High resource mobilization advantage can be reaped by the HR for the company.
- E-arrangement ensures serene and conducive interview atmosphere since less labour oriented.
- Facilitates recruiter name and their consulting partner branded at college campus which in turn multiplies the company popularity.

1.2 Advantages to Students

- Students can give interviews at their own individual personal space anytime/anywhere process based on their schedule.
- Student Profile branding at company or partner portals is ensured which in turn will benefit student professional visibility.
- Students are relieved from pandemonium or congestion on campuses otherwise which we would see during in any crowded job-fairs or events otherwise.
- Students can also constantly check back with company for any freelance, part-times, internships or projects available at regular intervals.

2. Benefits :

2.1 Benefits to Company

- Alignment of recruiter requirements anytime anywhere to the campus interview process available for companies due to quick information sharing facilities at Portals.
- Electronic Interviews can be executed anytime/anywhere as well per company convenience.
- E-interviews set ups facilitate easy access and user-friendly experience for overall recruitment management.
- HR Department can easily evaluate the proceedings of interview even from their remote or offshore locations.

- Easy provision of resource for part-time, projects and internships can also be made by the company.

2.2 Benefits to Students

- Easy alignment of practiced skills to apply on-line is possible for modern age generation at electronic interviews.
- Less laborious schedule will ease stress on student physique and intellect.
- Students can better know their employability acceptance progress by accessing online industry feedbacks at regular intervals.
- Student's individual profile is showcased on-line universally for better career opportunities.

3. Constraints :

3.1 Constraints to Company

- Lack of encouragement from company to fully automate recruiting process with fear of losing manual jobs is a constraint in the implementation process of e-interviews.
- The sourcing avenues may not have the IT atmosphere matching that of the company to execute the process.
- High expenses and costs may be involved in managing the recruitment software and its applications.
- Difficult to manually invigilate and supervise the interview proceedings.
- Possibilities of glitch of on-line process due to various technical reasons are also evident.

3.2 Constraints to Students

- Lack of invigilator or manual supervision may leave students confused while navigating online.
- Students tend to take the schedule light and easy as they believe they can access the process anytime anywhere.
- Inability of the student to access internet, applications and system may lead to their innocence and ignorance on job offer status.
- Students tend to become lethargic and lazy in absence of high pressure corporate

environment which otherwise generally seen at physical campus interviews.

- Student face image failure when companies drop profiles of unqualified or rejected profiles from their portals.

4. Disadvantages :

4.1 Disadvantages to Company

- Installation and implementation of process may become rigid and tedious as company needs to configure and map the IT infrastructure services to that of the college.
- Invalidity of electronic process if the sourcing avenue does not have or support the required IT environment of the company.
- Technical error and system lag can delay the entire e-recruitment process.
- The quality of manpower obtained post the process may not be satisfactory as compared with physical campus recruitment.
- Creation of negative image for recruiter if the e-recruitment process fails due to various technical and non-technical reasons.

4.2 Disadvantages to Students

- Any confusion at any stage of e-recruitment may lead to demotivation among students rendering the event ineffective.
- Student Absence as well not accessing the interview modules online can again render the process ineffective affecting student career.
- Rigidity and Procrastination may lead the student to lose control on administering himself at company web portals and thereby miss out job opportunities.
- On-line interview dependence may lead to total innocence and ignorance of real world physical interview process existence.
- Image failure will depress students at campus, if company rejects and removes their profile from company database.

Table1 : Issues and Factors for Muthoot Finance On-line Recruitment Model using ABCD framework

Determinant Issues identified for Stakeholders of Muthoot Finance’s Online Process as per Framework				
Key Attributes	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
E-Process Schedule	Ease of Implementation	Methodical & Organized	Student Casual Take	Impending Technical Issues
E-Process Flexibility	Highly Adaptability	Free of Trouble	Time Consuming	Lack of HR Intervention
E-Process Administration	Anytime/Anywhere	Own-Supervision	Apathy	Lack of Adoption
E-Process Usage, Relevance and Applicability	Conducive for Career	Ease of Alignment	Lack of Process Comprehension	Lack of Initiative

VI. Critical Constituent Elements of Muthoot Finance’s Online Process as per ABCD model

Table 2 : Advantageous Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

Focus Area	Key Attributes	Advantageous Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Muthoot Finance Ltd.	E-Process Schedule	Ease of Implementation	Online Approach
Student	E-Process Schedule	Highly Adaptive	Easy to execute

Table 3 : Beneficial Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

Focus Area	Key Attributes	Beneficial Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Muthoot Finance Ltd.	E-Process Flexibility	Organized and Methodical	Easy Flow
Student	E-Process Flexibility	Self-Supervision	Simple to work

Table 4 : Constraining Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

Focus Area	Key Attributes	Constraining Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Muthoot Finance Ltd.	E-Process Administration	Control Issues	No direct control
Student	E-Process Administration	Casual Take	Lack of Interest

Table 5 : Disadvantageous Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

Focus Area	Key Attributes	Disadvantageous Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Muthoot Finance Ltd.	E-Process Usage, Relevance and Applicability	Unable to fully automate	Process Integration Shortcomings
Student	E-Process Usage, Relevance and Applicability	Lack of Initiative	Lethargy and Procrastination

VII. Findings :

The critical constituent elements extracted from Muthoot Finance Limited’s recruitment process above as per ABCD model brought about certain quantifiable criterions for determination on the viability of the online process. These elements are derivative out of the various attributes affecting determinant issues pertaining to key elements endorsed by the focus group.

VIII. Suggestions or Optimum Solutions for process betterment :

The advanced suggestion would be even to have the group discussion GD online through group video conferencing to make it fully automated. A request is also forwarded here to include a pre-placement lecture video by company HR to encourage and motivate the placement seeking students.

IX. Conclusion :

As concluding remarks, we have studied the determinant issues and various key factors affecting Muthoot Finance's e-campus recruitment model using ABCD Model. The analysis identified numerous key affecting attributes for various determinant issues under four constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages. The analysis brought out important critical constituent elements under the constructs which satisfied the objectives of the model to benefit stakeholders.

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